

MEGAPROJECTS MANAGEMENT - A CHALLENGING, COMPLEX & RISKY ENDEAVOR

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Abstract: The paper provides insights on management aspect of megaprojects and the complexity surrounding it. The world is currently witnessing incredible megaprojects that are leaving a symbolic mark on our globe and altering it in ways that have never been seen before and affecting every individual lives. Megaprojects are a special category of very large, complicated, emblematic, and expensive projects. Megaprojects may be both a boon or a burden; when they're completed successfully, their creators enjoy the rewards of fame and fortune, but when they fail or get abandoned, entire businesses and their reputations are often destroyed. Megaprojects has been the focus of debate and study for the past few decades, but there is little in the way of written material on the management aspect to deal with the complexities it brings along. The paper gives with the insights of megaprojects and emerging field of megaproject management; the current problem plaguing the field of megaproject management and how the industry is thriving to improvise the practices and arrive at a long lasting and robust solution. The paper also presents the complexity and challenges involved in executing a megaproject, and how it creates opportunities as well as sinkholes without a way of it. The paper also answers on why megaprojects are still preferred despite the low success rate and concludes on the advancements that adds positivity to the megaproject practitioners and institutionalists. The article argues that megaproject management needs to be refurbished and conventional procedures, practices and strategies needs a major overhaul. A few of notable recommendation and good practices are listed. This work contributes towards the field of megaprojects and the management aspect of these giants for practitioners and institutionalists to get better insights and focus.

Index Terms - Megaproject, Megaproject Management, Challenges, Complexity, Project Management Risks

I. INTRODUCTION

This paper provides with an outline of the megaproject universe, the challenges in executing these giants, and the elements that makes it more complex. The paper differentiates the key aspects between conventional project management to the megaproject management, which is a distinguished area of expertise. This paper also looks at the different social and economic challenges that these megaprojects have resulted and may cause.

Megaproject overruns and cost burden incurred are humongous. The additional capital spent hints at wasted public funds that may have been used more productively elsewhere. Another issue is that feasible projects may have been overlooked in favor of high-profile ones, and if the initial cost estimates had been accurate and realistic may result different selections. While megaprojects are criticized at one end, other view them as promising. Without megaprojects, the world wouldn't have been so connected and advanced. The large projects are equally handling the role of national development and vision statements. Consider the example of Eiffel tower, which has yielded France the revenue more than 100's of times its build cost over the century, and the impact it had on economy of France and its tourism is phenomenal. Megaprojects are monumental and its benefits are beyond the boundaries of project economics. The Panama Canal for example built at an equivalent today cost of \$8 Bn, is currently earning \$3- 4 Bn annually and contributes majorly to the nation's economy and existence. China has been experiencing a surge in megaprojects and have transformed itself to a world leader in megaprojects in the last three decades and has benefited the most of it. Megaprojects bring in great economic value and transform the footprints of nations if the right fit is selected and successfully executed.

Within the scope boundaries of megaprojects management, this study investigates the standard procedures used in project and program management today. The study demonstrates that traditional project management techniques fail to deliver the desired results for megaprojects and why this is the case. The difficulties that megaprojects face in the real world and the intricacies that set them apart from other megaprojects are discussed in this paper.

II. MEGAPROJECTS – SIGNIFICANCE & TREND

Megaprojects are the most common approach to build large infrastructure these days, and are essential to global economies. The growth of a country's economy and standard of living depend on its level of infrastructure. Businesses and individuals in any country have an immediate need for a well-maintained infrastructure. Megaprojects need huge investment that features private investors, international financial institutions, combination of investors and also both national and supranational governments. Megaprojects are becoming the dominant deployment model for assets and services across numerous sectors, industries, and organizations. The spread is across Infrastructure, Oil & Gas, Utilities, Energy, Information technology, Manufacturing, Processing plants, Mineral extraction, Supply chain and Logistics, Business applications, Company's strategic initiative, Acquisitions and Mergers, Administrative systems, Financial institutions, Defense and Intelligence, Space and Aviation, Scientific research, Urban regeneration, Environmental restoration, Disaster management and so on (Flyvbjerg, 2017). Recently, Megaprojects have shifted from a peripheral activity primarily intended for privileged, developed nations to a global multitrillion-dollar enterprise that reverberates through every element of our existence, from the cost of keeping the lights on, to the products we buy, and to the means by which we get to work (Flyvbjerg, 2008). Megaprojects are known for being challenging, complicated, dangerous, and having many connections and dependencies. This is being observed that, infrastructure projects of ever-increasing size and scope are being planned and constructed throughout the globe (Elkhedr, 2018). Megaprojects are huge, compelling, expensive, contentious, and difficult projects. A country's economy could be severely impacted by significant cost overruns on government-backed projects, which could influence a nation's decision to vote against an incumbent administration (Love et al., 2012). Megaprojects fascinates and displays the human potential and its limit. Since megaprojects have become both a threat to and an inevitable part of a country's overall economy, they cannot be avoided if the country is to continue to prosper. For economic progress, the successful management of these megaprojects has become a must. Growing infrastructure needs, globalization, and modernization have sparked a flurry of megaprojects in the past two decades. Rapid global urbanization has generated increased investment in construction megaprojects. Megaprojects are huge and getting bigger, and they're being built more often and for more money (Thoufeeq, 2022).

Trends over last couple of decades show a significant increase in size and quantity of infrastructure projects. The call and outrage for the establishment of best in the class public infrastructure is continuous. According to Ansar et al., (2016), the governments are constantly increasing their public investment in order to generate employment opportunities through the construction of various types of physical infrastructure. Researchers have found that political, technological, economic, and aesthetic factors are driving the growth of megaprojects (Flyvbjerg, 2014). Megaprojects have shaped the global economy and emerging nations over the past decade. The construction of pipelines, the provision of natural gas, the development of new technology, the facility of food security, the development of environment and agriculture, the construction of wind farms and energy alternatives, the relief of urban overcrowding, the construction of better schools and medical facilities, and the renovation and upgrading of bridges, underground megastructure, and roads at the end of their useful lives, all of them need big investments to be executed as megaprojects (Bresnan et al 2003; Greiman 2013; Greiman, 2014).

Globalist cities can't function without massive urban renewal initiatives. The increase in such endeavors can be traced back to two trends that run in tandem and overlap. Global competition between cities has been heightened by two factors: first, the economic shift toward post-industrial civilizations, and second, the progress of neo-liberalization. Socioeconomic growth is often mentioned as one of the main reasons why megaprojects are built. These are expected to bring in a lot of good things, like new jobs and more economic activity. Quantifying these social and economic implications a statutory obligation for planning process. Most megaprojects have multiple effects at the same time, including social and economic ones. Based on their mode of occurrence, effects can be classified as direct, indirect, or induced across all dimensions. Direct societal effects include creating new employment opportunities, providing access to public services at lower costs, decreasing pollution levels, and improving people's health. Indirect social effects include changes to social infrastructures like transportation facilities and changes to the population, culture, or health (Miller and Blair, 2009; Nourelfath et al., 2022). Global competition has increased exponentially, forcing every economy to strengthen its economy, society, technology, and reputation. As a result, economies have strengthened their foundations by investing more in things like infrastructure. This has resulted in the undertaking and implementation of huge, complicated megaprojects with enormous resources and lengthy durations. A megaproject is typically characterized by its complexity, huge investment, indeterminacy, variable interaction, and changing environments, critical socio-political and external influences, and lengthy building period.

Megaprojects are frequently regarded as the most complicated and uncertain type of project because of the various stakeholder groups and influences, considerable investment, increased community involvement, complex decision-making environment, and potential of risk. Moreover, even with precalculated and calibrated project specifics, the unpredictability of megaprojects indicates a propensity for risk. Without a doubt, the failure of a megaproject usually leads to the bankruptcy of an investment firm or extremely heavy financial losses, and this has far-reaching consequences. Megaprojects are once again playing a significant role in the progress of less developed countries, despite concerns about their impact. The outcomes of megaprojects, as argued by many, can be understood by employing a "politics of vision," which arises when multiple factors and levels of analysis collide (Cornelio et al., 2021). Vast people think they're great for making a "big push" toward modernization, while others warn of the many drawbacks and possible failure of such programs.

III. MEGAPROJECTS MANAGEMENT – A RISKY ENDEAVOR

Increasing number of megaprojects are being executed in environments of high complexity and uncertainty (Qazi et al., 2021), necessitating less rigid and more flexible methods to effective risk management. The amount of money the government spends on megaprojects is continuing to rise. Having sustainable public finances and economic growth depends on the performance and efficiency of spending; however, when it comes to economy, most megaprojects end up being disastrous, raising concerns and increasing the risk involved (Montrimas et al., 2021). A complex structure in a megaproject is characterized by multiple interacting parts. Numerous threats will interact with the system because of the system's uncertainty and dynamics. Megaprojects that require

a lengthy completion period are typically subject to high risk, i.e. the possibility of an uncontrolled scenario due to the complex coexistence of social, financial, and political actors. As an example, infrastructure development rules and regulations will be impacted by a decline in state funding owing to an something we can't predict, like a pandemic, changes in the global economy, or a catastrophic natural disaster.

Risk is defined as an unpredictable circumstance that can have an effect on project activity (PMI, 2021). It is acknowledged that the risk, expenses and sophistication have exponentially increased in the last decade, hindering megaproject implementation. Megaprojects in a global setting combine higher levels of risk and complexity in multiple dimensions. Bent Flyvbjerg pioneered research in the field have slated megaprojects as inherently dangerous due to their extensive planning prospects, complicated interactions and frequent turnover of management team leaves a weak leadership. A gradual shift in the project basic aims or objective are viewed as catastrophic to the project, eventually leading to cost overruns, delays, and fewer benefits than expected, which hurts the project's viability. Inaccurate information about prices, schedules, benefits, and risks coupled with inadequate budget and time contingencies, result a low success rate to most of megaprojects (Flyvbjerg, 2008). Megaprojects are complex, high-risk ventures. Conventional risk management involves isolating, insuring, transferring, or avoiding risk. This technique to evaluating the progress of a Megaproject is frequently short-sighted. Many crucial aspects are sometimes disregarded.

Inadequate risk sharing was a major failure reason in the majority of multibillion dollar endeavors because contextual underestimate and decision-making is being ineffective and being performed in isolation. Meticulous preparation and an awareness of uncertainty can limit unfavorable consequences (Mišić & Radujković, 2015). Rothengatter (2019) said that megaprojects are getting too difficult to manage because they take too long to plan and get approvals, and there are often conflicts between public and private actors' competing values and interests, which takes too much time and money. There is evidence that legal and political factors contribute to implementation difficulties (Altshuler & Luberoff, 2020). Long planning and development causes the project in dilemma, and several ruling parties may have political duties. Changes in political power between the planning and execution phases may require transferring roles or modifying the project to meet a new strategic intent, altering the plans. The inability to comprehend the fundamental structure of complex systems in megaprojects triggers the majority of megaprojects to fall short of their intended results and benefits. There are several difficulties, including a lack of preparation for dealing with potential risks, worries about the future that prevent long-term planning, a lack of lasting impact on learning, and subpar overall performance. There is a substantial relationship between megaproject paradoxes and the planning methodologies and procedures now in use to the risk it poses to the megaprojects (Widiastuti et al., 2022).

Important risks, such as technical complexity and stakeholder management, require a systemic risk perspective. However, when the system is further disrupted by speed and acceleration, the internal socio-complexity of the project increases. The fact that projects are executed by human teams along with their response to project disruptions affects decision making that must be made considering all risk elements. Megaproject management shall device a way to set up adjustment variables affecting uncertainty and projected performance based on risk attitude (Qazi et al., 2021). Excessive risk aversion can result in profound mistrust, which counterproductively raises the risk level. We discovered that risk increases during adversarial construction and decreases during collaborative development. Excessive legal protections and penalties in contracts, which may take up pages and pages, could have the opposite effect of what was intended and make people more concerned with their own safety on the job than with adopting steps that would improve productivity. Excessive risk management can have negative effects on profitability and executive virility through contractor risk premiums and legal/litigation costs. In conditions plagued by distrust, the inherent problems of megaprojects are amplified dramatically.

The Iron triangle is a prevalent project success indication. Atkinson, (1999) contends that the megaproject success must be evaluated from broader perspectives, taking into account the interests of all key stakeholders. In the earliest phases of megaprojects, decision-making remains a crucial element, which than switches to cost, quality and satisfaction as the project phase transitions towards completion. The research suggests that certain decisions result in low levels of performance. These choices are motivated not merely by technical considerations but also by political goals. The difference between projected expenses and budget overruns is attributed to optimism bias (Flyvbjerg, 2008). A national risk is posed by optimism bias because the distribution of funds and resources typically constitutes a threat to national finances. In addition, the planning and implementation of long-term projects cannot be completed within several government terms. Consequently, they are frequently burdened with political restraints, heightening the economic, social, and political risks (Widiastuti et al., 2022). Up to 70 percent of the time, problems with fallacies emerge in feasibility studies. The significant effort that is applied into developing a feasibility study for multibillion projects are questioned and critiqued based on its accounting fundamentals. The danger of performing preliminary research with limited data and time is that it justifies inferior performance, setbacks, and unanticipated environmental and social issues. We must investigate why unforeseen issues and levels of performance persist throughout the deployment of megaprojects. It appears that we have not learned from past mistakes (Widiastuti et al., 2022).

Construction megaprojects rely heavily on technical decision-makings, which are contentious with significant risks due to technological complexity, a dynamic environment, and subject cognition. In megaproject management, it is crucial to identify technological decision-making risks and investigate their interplay (Tang et al., 2022). Over the course of a megaproject's entire life cycle—from conception to completion to ongoing maintenance—managers will encounter social risk management obstacles, such as competing interests among stakeholders, public skepticism, and even outright opposition (Xia & Xiang, 2022). Identifying and managing risks are the two most essential aspects of megaproject management. Recognizing potential risk variables has primary and secondary implications on the risk management process, but improved risk management can help with future outcome prediction. Therefore, project stakeholders may benefit from a comprehension of these high-risk and low-risk parts and components. Most studies find that execution risks are the biggest determinants affecting the success of construction megaprojects. Analyzing the risk for each different kind of project could be essential due to the fact that the nature of the project, its risk distribution, the stakeholders involved, and the amount of investment all play a role in determining how severe the risks are. In order to mitigate any potential losses and long-term issues in megaprojects, it is crucial to evaluate the various risk factors. It can help customize and

improve the decision-making environments in which projects are managed, especially large-scale ones. Therefore, in order to effectively achieve risk identification, risk severity assessment, inter risk connection, and risk distribution among the entities or stakeholders, risk assessments for megaprojects need to be treated as a special situation. This is necessary in order to achieve effective results (Chatpadhyay et al., 2021). It is required to instill regulations on megaproject management and the command of its execution for megaprojects requiring multibillion-dollar investments and a likelihood of being exposed to many risk pressures. Identifying inherent risk and avoiding it in a timely manner has always been difficult, particularly for megaprojects. Due to the fact that most of the megaprojects are primarily reliant on regional circumstances, community acceptance, and authority consent, they are exposed to political risk, which not only increases project time but also poses substantial financial risk. Inadequate funding and resources are also detrimental to the endeavor. However, the influence of these risk variables' severity and complexity differs across megaprojects. These risk factors may have a greater influence on certain projects than others. Identifying risks and assigning them to project stakeholders helps improve the outcome of megaprojects by mitigating these risks. Megaprojects necessitate an evaluation of interrelationships between hazards in order to classify them appropriately, to aid handling and management of risk effectively.

IV. MEGAPROJECTS MANAGEMENT – AN EMERGING NOTION

Megaproject management, on the other hand, has only been established during the past couple of decades, although the discipline of project management has been evolving for centuries. The original goal of megaproject management was to facilitate scientific and technological endeavors, but currently it is expected to fulfil a far broader range of complicated and large-scale projects. It is unclear, how the profession of megaproject management could live up to such lofty goals (Sankaran et al., 2021). Project portfolio management, project management offices, and project governance all emerged in the years after the year 2000 in response to the industry's growing recognition that megaprojects are strategic tools requiring specialized skill sets and organizational levels. Due to the magnitude and complexity of these endeavors, robust management is even more significant in this environment. In recent decades, megaprojects and megaproject management have spread to several industries, including less complicated contexts and the mass manufacturing/consumer goods sector. The bigger the complexity of the project, the more factors must be addressed for project initiation and conclusion, as well as for determining the megaproject's short and long-term effects. The size and scope of megaprojects complicate not only closure but the very idea of a lifecycle of the megaproject.

Misinterpretation of project management through a technical perspective intends to achieve a scenario based on logic and science rather than establishing new possibilities in the context of disruption and unanticipated contingencies of everyday practice (Rolfe et al., 2016). Megaprojects have become more widespread and increasing exponentially over the last two decades, and the management of these projects has become a separate field within engineering and management. From the lesson learned and megaprojects database, major percentage of megaprojects have surprisingly low success rates concerning achievement of objectives, growth, ecological sustainability, and community acceptability. The project management teams in coordination with sponsors and key stakeholders are responsible for planning, monitoring, controlling, manage changes and mitigate its impact to the project's scope. Megaprojects due to its massive scale, provide significant issues for planning, evaluating, and managing, with consequences felt well beyond the megaproject boundaries in terms of economy, society, environment, and territory. The profession of megaproject management has become more crucial as businesses have grown more complicated, implemented new concepts, products, and services, or sought to enhance already existing ones. In the views of Pellegrinelli et al., (2015), megaproject management coordinates, communicates, aligns, manages, and controls processes to achieve synergy, benefits, outcomes, or vision. Megaproject management is a new project management profession that emphasizes tremendous level of leadership and professional development (Flyvbjerg, 2014). Managers of megaprojects, also termed as program or portfolio managers, are tasked with steering the megaproject through the unpredictability of a developing strategy, providing decisive leadership, and resolving cultural and political conflicts among all parties involved.

The conventional project management theory and industry tools are inadequate to manage complexity, that needs a resolution. The management of megaprojects also necessitates a substantial modification of strategic and financial plans to fit an environment of dynamic, complex, independent events, probabilities, and various stakeholders. The behavioral aspect of decision making is another area in which project management principles, methodologies, and theoretical concepts have proven insufficient to address the difficulties of complex megaprojects, which require greater knowledge and experience (Greiman, 2014). Business project managers now have a far broader range of concerns, including risk management, governance, program and portfolio management, an elevated level of investment, and the realization of project outcomes. Megaproject management to date has not been able to establish an successful proven execution model, and they mainly rely on a break-and-fix model, in which the project is carried out until it breaks, at moment which a fix is introduced with a change in the plan, that eventually compromises the main goals (Flyvbjerg, 2014).

Megaprojects are distinguished by the vast sums of resources they demand, an ever-changing environment in which to complete them, cutting-edge technological processes, and an infinite number of possible interconnections. So, this definition says that megaprojects are complicated, but it doesn't cover all possible levels of complexity because it only looks at task complexity. There are four more layers to think about: social, cultural, operational, and cognitive complexity. There are many ways to describe complexity. One that is straightforward and easy to understand defines complexity as the number of distinct components in a system and the complexities as the important interactions among these elements. The Luhmannian system theory defines complexity as the degree of a decision field's manifoldness, interconnectedness, and consequential influence. According to Brockmann et al., (2007) Four factors cause project complexity: (1) utilized resource; (2) context; (3) degree of technical and scientific expertise necessary; and (4) quantity and interconnection of workflow elements. The completion of these megaprojects represents a new frontier in terms of scale, expertise, and technology. Complexity in tasks, structures, goals, implementation, and management and organizations is a common hallmark of such (Baccarini, 1996; Brockmann & Girmscheid, 2007).

The usage of robotics and IoT applications in project management is on the rise, and principle-based techniques and AI based tactics are being adopted to enhance traditional project management practices. By comparing premodern and contemporary project

management and explaining how various items were derived environment, socioecological regime, technical specialty, megaproject management is a management innovation that has successfully migrated to address global needs supported by socio-technical frameworks. (Sankaran et al., 2021). According to the Rethinking Project Management Network, projects of the future will be "multidisciplinary, porous, contestable, and open to negotiation throughout". Megaprojects are affected by "political legitimacy discourse and social as well as power plays," as noted by Gauthier & Ika, (2012). In the ultra-modern social environment, megaproject is a large group of people working together entrenched within the framework of a community and perpetual transformation. Morris (2013) suggests rethinking megaproject management as a whole to solve the gaps between portfolio, program, and project management (Sankaran et al., 2021).

Managing large projects, or "megaprojects," has inspired a wealth of writing on a wide range of topics, all of which is essential to the field. However, it falls short in its coverage of the subject matter and the depth of its analysis of project management systems through project lifecycle. Most writing on the topic focuses on just one facet of a megaproject, such as its price tag, timeline, safety, risks, uncertainty, stakeholder management, stages, causes of problems, successes, or obstacles. (Ashkanani & Franzoi, 2022 ;Wang, 2022). The current body of literature on megaproject management has significant knowledge gaps that need to be investigated further and shed light on how they affect the preparation, management, and completion of these massive, complex projects. The majority of published publications fail to conclusively show or confirm the usefulness of the proposals for enhanced megaproject management, and they also fail to provide clear guidance for future study and/or industrial implementation. The literature and industry often praise techniques, methodologies, and best practices that are not comprehensive enough and often not easy or immediately adaptable because they focus on the particularities of a given megaproject. While many scholarly books address certain aspects of megaproject management, they rarely cover the complete system. Therefore, further study is needed to handle megaproject management in depth, exhaustively, and efficiently in the academic literature, especially considering the complexity of such a subject and the many gaps and issues that have yet to be fully addressed.

a. CHALLENGES LURING MEGAPROJECT MANAGEMENT

How to plan and implement megaprojects is one of the most difficult challenges facing policymakers today. Megaprojects including dams, infrastructure, industries, motorways, passageways, and airports, are now common. These megaprojects are both symbolic and functionally significant, and they are capable of having enormous effects on the destiny of regions and countries. On the other hand, problems tend to multiply in conjunction with the expansion of a project's scope.; large-scale initiatives frequently fail to accomplish their initial goals, incurring significant costs and unplanned consequences that can only be realized with tremendous difficulty and agony (Hall, 1982; Hirschman, 1967; Szyliowicz, 1991). Megaprojects are challenging initiatives where change and uncertainty are frequent occurrences. The ability to recognize and manage risks over the course of the project will determine its success. This means that for these initiatives to be successful, they need to be planned, structured, funded, and managed in a way that takes change into account, clearly defines risk, and minimizes the effects of late costs, functionality, and schedule (Chatterjee & Purnendu, 2015).

Modern advancements and technologies have become a significant and rapidly expanding component of an increasing number of significant megaprojects. Large technology initiatives seem to perform significantly worse than other large projects. Implementation of cutting-edge technologies or innovative items has been observed to sabotage multiple projects. Since megaprojects involve many vested parties, often conflicting, interests, many of the people involved are looking out for themselves. Furthermore, participants in global megaprojects have complex processes, documentation requirements, documentation solutions, management practices, and organizational cultures that are all unique from one another. Each stakeholder works under several managers to accomplish their parts of a demanding schedule with rigorous targets, intensive efforts, distant construction segments, and growing onsite interaction issues (Sabek & McCabe, 2017). Megaproject governance is extremely difficult due to the characteristics of sophisticated funding schemes, innovative contracts, high-level visibility, untested technologies, delicate political nature, and various participants with opposing interests (Muller, 2014). To avoid problems with megaprojects, strict contractual agreements, governance structures, and governance regimes are required (Miller & Hobbs, 2005).

The significance of megaprojects in promoting economic expansion remains crucial across the world and have grown fast. However, as their number, size, and complexity have grown, so has the difficulty of planning, executing, and ultimately succeeding. Most face unexpected challenges and few achieve their original goals (Szyliowicz & Goetz, 1995). However, by the 1970s and the beginning of the 1980s, these strategic initiatives often ran late and over budget, "raising the question of how many enterprises and public institutions with varied cultures, aims, and experiences may be united in the execution of complex engineering megaprojects." A deeper understanding of the megaprojects' complex and uncertain difficulties was needed beyond scheduling, planning, and control. Such inquiries are relevant to various sectors and situations which delivers megaprojects (Ahola & Davies, 2012).

Many megaproject proponents now recognize that the prerequisites for project success must include a multidisciplinary approach that incorporates elements beyond engineering. Such elements include robust project management, environmental assessment, public participation, risk assessment and monitoring, political champions and many more. Yet, despite the rhetorical pledges time and time again, the lessons of the past have not been learned and the same problems arise. It is not real to say that the next megaproject will avoid the pitfalls of past failures. The track record of large-scale projects does not lend confidence to claims that things are getting better (Moore, 1998). Complexities, Technologies and trends, Environmental and Sustainability challenges, Public Engagement and Influence, Political motives, Geopolitics, Global instability, Pandemics, Sanctions etc., and many other factors are further posing challenges to deliver successful megaprojects.

A megaproject's success hinges heavily on the quality of its management., the methods that are selected in proportion to the obstacles that the project presents, as well as the model that is used to judge organization's efficiency in completing the assignment. The accomplishment of a huge challenge is primarily dependent on the management that is used, the methods that are selected in proportion to the obstacles that the project presents, as well as the model that is used to judge the progress of the project organization.

More open and equitable planning and decision-making processes are also needed to better serve people's needs and improve the performance of development projects (Moore, 1998). Rolstadås et al., (2014) describes the two distinct management approaches: The prescriptive technique places an emphasis on the procedural aspects of the organization of the project, such as the regulating papers and the processes. The adaptive method prioritizes the establishment and cultivation of a project's structure and culture, as well as the dedication of its team members.

The social and economic gains from megaprojects can be substantial. The management of such massive endeavors is notoriously difficult. It's not uncommon for decision-makers to have to cope with long-standing tensions and strike a delicate balance between competing needs as they implement these unique and complicated solutions, which include numerous stakeholders from a wide range of industries. Because of the increased public and political interest, megaprojects require more stringent protocols and extensive reporting than smaller projects in the name of transparency. And yet, the unique and inventive results expected from megaprojects necessitate a considerable level of risk-taking and novel approaches (Wiewiora & Desouza, 2022).

b. MEGAPROJECT MANAGEMENT – COMPLEXITY MAKES THE DIFFERENCE

Over the course of large projects, many different events and interactions, some of which were planned and others not which takes place, and a megaproject is finished as a consequence of this complex web of shifting players, procedures, and environments. There are several hurdles to managing megaprojects, regardless of industry (private, public, non-profit, or miscellaneous). Complexity is the one word that distinguishes normal projects and the megaprojects (Hall, 1982; Sanvido et al., 1992; Szyliowicz, 1991; Szyliowicz & Goetz, 1995). Geraldi et al., (2011) characterizes project complexity as fundamental, ambiguity, dynamic, accelerated, and socio-political. Improvements in methodologies and technologies for managing complex projects, such as megaprojects, are necessary. Saynisch (2010) stated that the methodologies need to be adapted for each individual project as it develops over time. It is therefore impossible to establish "one size fits all" approaches, as these adjustments should take into consideration the client's particular cultural influences, stressing the need of the management's sensitivity in designing the strategy. Management in the increasingly popular hybrid approach to project management each contributes their own set of practices, processes, and tools, all of which may be merged, tested, analyzed, and altered to meet the specific requirements of each given project.

Megaproject management, according to Guo & Sheng, (2018), is an organized approach whose primary goal is to solve complicated organization obstacles. Typically, complexity is separated into two categories: both the complexity within an organization and the complexity of its environment outside the organization. The majority of the components that make up external complexity are the temporal, societal and the cultural complexity. Neglecting external complexity could have devastating effects for megaproject management, even leading to failure (T. Wang et al., 2022). Several studies in recent years have addressed the problem of megaprojects failing to meet their performance targets, with the failure being attributed to poor planning for complexity and uncertainty. Although highly skilled personnel and ample resources have been employed, this and other difficulties inherent to megaprojects remain unresolved. In order to deal with the complicated and uncertain character of megaprojects, sophisticated planning is a necessity and this relies heavily on the decision-making procedure (Widiastuti et al., 2022). System engineering and technological complexity are widely recognized, yet for megaprojects, uncertainty and stakeholder complexity remain the greatest obstacles. These challenges can be overcome by avoiding the urge to force somebody's benefit with construction firms, embracing some deficit of predictability and command, being diligent in attempting to bring the different viewpoints that are always present in megaprojects to the table, and maintaining a coherent approach that allows progress-directed decision making rather than conflict-avoidance trade-offs. However, many of these management processes were successful for megaprojects a few generations ago and might lead to a brighter future for upcoming megaprojects (Lenfe & Loch, 2016).

The phrase megaproject always emphasizes to massive and complex projects. Contextual unpredictability, such as general economic fluctuation and market instability, adds to the already substantial challenges of managing these megaprojects (Hu et al., 2015). Morris, (2013) says that a big or hard project can be handled by breaking it up into smaller projects and making each of those projects easier. In practice, a megaproject is made up of many smaller projects with similar goals. Temporary clients or monitoring teams selected by governments have a tough time managing the complexity of megaprojects and completing their objectives. In the same way as businesses and other long-lasting institutions (Dosi et al., 2000), temporary client organizations must establish and retain the capacity to execute megaproject construction and achieve predetermined goals. Consequently, the need to establish a program organizational capabilities framework from the client's perspective (Le, et al., 2015). New megaproject investors, as well as social and cultural transformations, add to the uncertainty of megaproject management in developing countries. The external complexity of managing megaprojects, which encompasses aspects of time, society, and culture, has grown substantially as a result of this context-specific unpredictability (Zolin et al., 2009). This complexity has an effect on the management of both organizations and stakeholders, as well as on the planning, procurement, monitoring, and control of projects, and the analysis and management of risks. The fascinating assortment of recognized practice, proprietary products, agreed standards, regularized methods, stories, tradition, urban legends, rituals, statements, firmly held convictions, and bias in methodology that surrounds the material assembled in megaproject management methodologies is not to be underestimated.

Megaproject management theories and existing literature raises concerns for the need of a framework. It is evident that megaproject management frameworks cannot be universal. Thus, megaproject management depends on project type, industry, culture, complexity, and other factors. This understanding led to subordinate megaproject management methods. PMI's construction and government sector extensions and culture-specific project management methods are the outcomes. IT project management is unique ("Agile Project Management" is an example). Construction accepts "planners" and "estimators" but no other businesses. This indicates that megaproject management strategies must be modified for diverse contexts. The megaproject world needs a flexible and rigorous megaproject management system (Ofer Zwikael & John R. Smyrk, 2019).

Parties to a contract are more likely to be defensive, contentious, and distrustful when using the conventional methods of delivering projects under transactional contracts. Due to the rising complexity and unpredictability of the construction sector, leading to inefficient project teams and unsatisfactory project deliverables (Alashwal & Fong, 2015; Ferrianto et al., 2016). This theory of adapting to complexity continues to be a core strength of NASA's project management in extremely complex, risky, and uncertain environments. The principle is based on the concept of leaving no room for error, and the mentality is that unless there is absolute certainty that nothing bad can happen, flying is extremely risky. In contrast, Boeing adopted a well-planned, rigorous, and comprehensive approach to project management, in which phases are clearly defined and tasks are completed sequentially within each phase. Boeing follows a highly organized and logical program to achieve each goal (Shenhar & Holzmann, 2017). Each framework possesses unique advantages and disadvantages. Megaprojects are difficult to oversee because of their complexity. In the real world, decision makers frequently use basic techniques to deal with unforeseen complications. The current methods for managing such massive projects are not enough for identifying and resolving the complications that arise throughout their execution (Wiewiora & Desouza, 2022). Relationship management is viewed as crucial for bettering relationship quality and attaining project success in the face of greater tensions in governance because of the need to address the risks and conflicts inherent to megaprojects. Three distinct configurations, such as relational ties, structural bonds, and contractual roles play an important part in defining relationship quality (Wang et al., 2021). Managing megaprojects calls for a willingness to change tactics and a clear division of labor between the project's stakeholders. Megaprojects should be delivered in collaboration with clients, not for clients (Denicol & Davies, 2022).

The complexity of a megaproject is proportional to the number of system components and the nature of their interdependence because of the sheer scale of the undertaking. The complexity framework encompasses the interconnectedness of organizational, technical, and ecological complexity. Stakeholders, geographical context, political climate, economic factors, and cultural norms all contribute to the tangled web of factors that make up a given environment complexity. On basis of the literature assessment, four main factors contribute majorly to project complexity: variety, unpredictability, interdependence, and dynamicity (F. Jia et al., 2022). The design and execution of megaprojects are complicated due to their size, which calls for the coordination of a wide range of agencies and groups operating in different jurisdictions, extensive financial and resource capacities, and a political climate. Due to rapidly changing circumstances that necessitate the modification of specific goals, objectives, and tendencies, megaprojects exhibit uncertain dynamics (Giezen, 2012). Each undertaking faces unique complexities relating to its initial environmental, social, and political settings, in addition to its financial features. Megaproject complexity affects productivity, expenditure, and quality (Rothengatter, 2019). The harmful impact on the environment and local communities, as well as the relocation of people, have led some to criticize megaprojects, which are typically led by a top-down and technocratic authority system. How large-scale initiatives are conceived, decided upon, and governed are complex by their very nature. These considerations are affected not just by the logical thought that typically leads the course of contemporary urban planning but also by a wide range of externalities that are both dynamic and uncertain. In large-scale projects, perfect rationality and linear planning are never possible. Planners and decision-makers often attempt to address issues with limited data and means (Baccarini, 1996). According to Brockmann et al., (2007), creative and adaptable solutions to problems might be sparked by the unforeseen obstacles that develop during the planning of such efforts. With so many different people and organizations having a hand in the design of megaprojects, it's clear that a fresh method is required to create a coherent framework for studying these interrelationships (Widiastuti et al., 2022).

Understanding the complexity of megaprojects is essential for completing them successfully. With the help of complexity theory, we can understand why an adaptive, coevolving, and self-organizing approach to planning is best suited to the nature of such fluid endeavors. It's crucial to keep in mind the complexity of the planning process, as it's possible to run into support or opposition from many stakeholders while working on a project. Increasingly, communication and interaction are crucial in complicated projects due to the inherent uncertainty of such undertakings (Roo & Silva, 2010). Due to the unpredictability of socioeconomic and political situations, it is important to investigate how a rational communicative planning approach to megaprojects might increase stakeholder commitment and flexibility within a dynamic situation. Megaprojects often require a large number of people to work together on a single solution (Widiastuti et al., 2022). Collaborative processes, as proposed by Innes & Booher, (2010), are more likely to succeed if viewed as complex adaptive systems. Stakeholders must be brought in during the planning stages of a megaproject. With a wide enough range of perspectives and expertise, they can restructure themselves. Paradoxes define social and political unrest, and complexity theories provides a framework for comprehending these issues and their tangled connections to logical methods. Understanding the complexity and volatility of planning for megaprojects is important because it motivates us to think outside the box when confronted with challenges. Technocracy and result-oriented decision making should be more closely aligned. To what extent can planning be a component of the answer in complicated projects is still an open question (Widiastuti et al., 2022). When a project is hard to understand, predict, and manage, we call it complicated. (Vidal et al., 2011). Complexity is introduced into megaproject management procedures due to the large number of design, engineering, and construction requirements that today's construction megaprojects must fulfil to meet high expectations of stakeholders (Jia et al., 2011). The presence of overlapping phases, several stakeholders, and systems of knowledge all contribute to the complexity of a megaproject management environment (Widforss & Rosqvist, 2015). When numerous projects of varying sizes and due dates compete for the same set of resources, the complexity of management rises even higher (Rostami & Oduoza, 2017).

Such contractors are expected to keep everyone involved performing at a high level, yet failing to account for complications may cause projects to derail (Hagan et al., 2011). They need integrated techniques to successfully manage cross-functional interdependencies and conflicting agendas, since they can't use the same methods to deal with the new kinds of complexity-related uncertainty (Mishra et al., 2018; Safo-Kantanka et al., 2019). In order to deal with complex projects, businesses should implement solid control mechanisms (Widforss & Rosqvist, 2015). Specifically, PMO's are created as an efficient form of integrated and centralized supervision (Cavalcanti et al., 2017). According to practitioners' perceptions, the primary reasons why megaprojects are so difficult to complete were the coexistence and interrelationships between complexity components. This result corroborates the view that a project's complexity is best conceptualized and evaluated in terms of a trend that develops over time, as opposed to a static list or hierarchy of isolated aspects of complexity. Stakeholder interactions, inexperience, and inexperience were the top three variables that increased the project's complexity (Bilgin et al., 2022).

Megaproject complexity plays an important role in driving innovation. In order to manage complexity and enhance megaproject delivery, there has been a rise in creative approaches. The literature on megaproject management lacks in-depth examinations of the Innovation and project complexity relationship. Analysis of innovative features and their relationship with project complexity is essential in progressing future. Megaprojects are starting to embrace new ideas and innovations. Because of the inherent risk and uncertainty in the novel methods, complexity is likely to increase. Even though the topic of project complexity has been covered extensively, the connection between complexity and the rising rate of innovation is less well understood (Cantarelli & Genovese, 2021). Indicators like cost, time, and quality used to be all that was needed to evaluate a megaproject's success; now, however, the entire project's lifespan and post-delivery state must also be taken into account (Wu et al., 2020).

V. RECOMMENDATIONS AND CONCLUDING OBSERVATIONS

It is apparent that early warning systems and preventative measures shall be communicated clearly to all key stakeholders to take quick and aligned decisions. Also, to add, a robust and skillful project management team is essential to keep projects on track and to avoid major cost overruns, scope creep, and missed deadlines. To achieve a higher degree of accountability, the project selection procedure must be founded on facts and be open. Investors and owners must be involved in the formation of the project team. They need more than just a theoretical understanding of how the project should run. They must devise a comprehensive, workable plan to address foreseeable occurrences such as dealing risks associated with quality, rising contractor costs, and the need to replace a high-tech supplier. The project must assemble a team with all required skills, such as technological and legal regulatory skill, contract administration, regulatory hurdles, participant engagement, and governmental and local connections.

When megaprojects fail, it is becoming increasingly clear that they are akin to the traditional bull: one bull is sufficient to destroy the entire store. Similarly, it is becoming apparent to all parties that action must be taken. Cost miscalculation and the frequency of budget overruns in the UK was high enough to prompt the chancellor to ask for a Green Book on the subject and its management (HM Treasury, 2003). As a result of this, many other nations took similar measures. Legislators and governments are beginning to recognize that with national fiscal stress and uncertain national budgets, the expense of conventional megaproject management is excessive. In 2011, the Cabinet Office and HM Treasury in the United Kingdom established the Major Projects Authority with the direct order from the Prime Minister to handle all important government-funded and -delivered projects and offer recommendations on their administration. The authority created the world's first Significant Projects Leadership Academy in 2012, in collaboration with Oxford University, to formally educate and certify all central government project managers in the United Kingdom. As private finance for megaprojects outside of the government has increased during the last two decades, banking institutions, capital funds, and pension funds have gained a stronger role in management. When it comes to megaproject management, private funding is hardly a silver bullet.; in certain cases, they may significantly exacerbate them (Hodge & Greve, 2009). Investors and bankers do not blindly trust the cost and profitability projections made by project leaders and promoters because private investors are putting their own money at risk. The banking sector routinely engages in independent estimation, due diligence, and risk assessments, and these services are provided by in-house specialists (Flyvbjerg, 2013). The myth that a single prediction or business case can convey all of the information about a project is refuted.

South Korea exhibits a promising method. In order to gather accurate information on costs and benefits, in 2005, PIMAC was founded as a hub for public and private infrastructure investment management. PIMAC evaluates public megaprojects, conducts feasibility studies, and evaluates value-for-money. Nearly half of the projects assessed by PIMAC have been rejected thus far. Prior to PIMAC, 3% of applications were rejected. In order to address these obstacles, a number of countries have created governance structures for the larger projects. Norway pioneered this approach in 2000, to serve as a framework for large-scale public initiatives. Volden & Samset, (2017) describe the Norwegian framework and its results, including some really encouraging ones. Similar regulations have been enacted in other nations. This central government project governance schemes in Norway is than followed by countries like UK, Denmark, Netherlands, Canada and Sweden. Each and every forecast is designed for central government administration of projects with high costs, risk, complexity, or innovation. For the first time in 2003, the UK Treasury required all ministries to establish and implement processes for major public projects to reduce "optimism bias." Initiatives that ignore this prejudice will not receive funding, and mechanisms have been established to do so (Flyvbjerg et al., 2004). For the first time in 2004, the Dutch Parliamentary Committee held comprehensive public hearings to develop methods to prevent misinformation about significant infrastructure projects from reaching Parliament, the society, and the press. Because of cost overruns, the city of Boston filed a lawsuit against Big Dig's contractors (Flyvbjerg, 2007). It is immoral and possibly illegal for project sponsors, strategists, and executives to knowingly mislead legislators, administrators, investors, public, and media about a project's pros and cons. Legislation like Sarbanes-Oxley, for instance, considers it a crime to knowingly mislead facts in numerous situations, punishable by up to 20 years in prison in the US. The "obligation to truth" is integrated into the constitutions of most democracies and, more recently, company bylaws to enforce accountability. Deliberately misrepresenting costs and benefits, for whatever reason, violates this obligation. Thankfully, despite decades of extensive incompetence in the policy and planning of megaprojects, there are now indications of progress. Legislators and governments are realizing that national financial turmoil makes the usual method of planning and developing large-scale projects too costly. Reform is driven by non-infrastructure agencies and industries, increasing its likelihood of success. One of the most well-liked non-traditional techniques for delivering transportation system, and rail megaprojects is the design-build project delivery approach, which has seen an increase in usage. Although design-build is frequently used and is performing better than other forms, there is still a dearth of knowledge regarding how to efficiently plan and manage design for transportation projects. Transportation agencies lack knowledge on how to manage design efforts for major design-build projects and how to assign suitable design management tasks to various contractual partners (Gatti et al., 2014).

To manage a megaproject well, it is a must to figure out how complicated it is and make the management fit the type and the project's degree of difficulty. Because the complexity of different megaprojects varies widely, it's clear that "One-size-fits-none" (Shenhar, 2001). Shenhar & Dvir, (2007) presented a classification scheme for projects on the basis of four factors: novelty, technology, complexity, and pace, and emphasized the importance of adapting its management to its specific classification. Over the past two decades, scholars have studied several aspects of project complexity, including its identification, confinement,

categorization, sources, evaluation, and administration (Shi et al., 2018). If organizations can fragment project complexity to decision-making level, complex technical system design can be managed more effectively (Dodds et al., 2003).

Almost every project undergoes a cost benefit analysis and go-ahead decisions are justified by a calculated economic internal rate of return (ERR) applying a discount rate. The ERR drops significantly if the project investment goes higher than the plan, schedule gets elongated or the projection on the users decline, and vice versa. Sensitivities shall be clearly detailed and averaged values of ERR shall be considered, rather than being overoptimistic to roll the project to garner investments and support. An essential part of evaluating a project is making predictions about its potential future benefits and expenses. Cost-benefit evaluations are a tedious but necessary task for determining which initiatives should receive funding. The optimism bias problem of underestimating costs and overestimating gains is not a secret. To avoid squandering limited public investment dollars on subpar projects, it is important to use accurate projections and discount rates in project selection (Montrimas et al., 2021).

Hybrid methods to project management are essential for organizations to deal with diverse processes, contractual needs and project specifics (Copola Azenha et al., 2021). Technology megaprojects are integrating agile and traditional project management methods to achieve flexibility and adaptability. No empirical research has examined the effects of hybrid models that combine agile and traditional approaches on organizations. Thus, advice on project management technique selection has primarily been theoretical. Traditional and Agile project management are combined in hybrid project management. Large projects that need a defined process and structure but flexibility to adapt to changes employ it. Hybrid project management allows agile and flexible teams to succeed with structure. This method helps teams to adapt their plans and processes to changes while maintaining project momentum. Hybrid project management is commonly utilised for large projects that require plenty of team coordination. A hybrid approach has many benefits for managing huge projects. One benefit is enhanced efficiency, as teams can adjust to changes while maintaining structure and process. This technique helps teams to be flexible, as they may easily modify plans without affecting the project timeline. Hybrid project management ensures project quality since teams may resolve concerns rapidly. Finally, this strategy can reduce the risk of huge projects, as teams can recognize possible dangers and adjust accordingly during the course of development (Robert K. Wysocki, 2019).

Benefits from developing the right projects the right way are on par with costs from building the wrong projects the wrong way. There has never been a time when it was more important to pick the right projects and make an accurate assessment of their economic, societal, and environmental implications. Systematic and trustworthy megaproject knowledge has never been more crucial for policy, practice, and public discourse in this high-risk corporate and government sector (Flyvbjerg, 2008). Due to the tremendous global development of megaproject building practice in the last decade, more and more academic resources have been dedicated to studying these projects (Hu et al., 2015). Some governments have created governance plans for larger projects to address these issues. In 2000, Norway pioneered a comprehensive framework for managing large public projects. Despite decades of mismanagement, megaproject policy and planning are improving. As the following cases show, deception to start businesses is under fire. Megaproject cost overruns, benefit deficiencies, and risks can impact a whole nation or region's finances, as was the case for Greece's 2004 Olympic Games and Hong Kong's 1998 international airport. Legislators and governments are realizing that the traditional method of planning and developing large projects is too expensive. Reform is driven by outsiders, increasing its chances of success.

Efficiency in completing project activities is increased when a management team can rely on consistent and well-defined procedures; this frees up resources for experimentation. But at the same time, trying new things can be a great source of innovation, and can even help improve upon the methods being used in a megaproject. For effective management, it's important to place equal emphasis on both continuity and modernity. Largely ignorant decision-makers may choose stability or change without considering the other, with potentially disappointing results for the project. Decision-makers need to be alert for paradoxes and able to recognize emerging trends. Taking use of complexities, paradoxes allow decision-makers to create novel approaches to problems. Instead of avoiding or attempting to simplify ambiguous and difficult situations, decision-makers should open themselves up to paradoxes and consider other approaches. In order to foster and sustain paradoxical thought, project-based organizations should provide leadership training for decision makers (Wiewiora & Desouza, 2022).

In accordance with the organizational governance framework, project governance serves as an oversight function that includes the project lifecycle. By developing and documenting reliable project processes, it maintains command and guarantees the project's completion (Alie, 2015). The concept of project governance is gaining traction in the industry and enhances stakeholder management and helps with administrative and managerial tasks in public projects. Throughout the project's life cycle, project stakeholders can better understand and influence decisions, in transparency is enhanced by good project governance. By establishing a structure for accountability and benefits management, PG increases the likelihood of a successful project and helps it deliver on its business case. In addition, it provides a framework for systematically monitoring and responding to risks as they emerge during the course of a project's execution. Decision-making framework, project management tools, and organizational process structure support portfolios, programs, and projects deliver successfully (Fareed & Su, 2022). Project governance is often seen as the deciding element in how well a project turns out once it's put into action. The term "management of project management" denotes the upper levels of administration that project governance represents in relation to traditional project management. By bringing together the many parties involved in a project, it aids in mitigating risks throughout the project's duration (Luo et al., 2022).

Mindfulness is gaining popularity within project management, perhaps due to the positive impact it has shown to have on individuals, teams, and organizations in other areas of management. Mindfulness is a mental stance that allows us to respond to our surroundings with openness and curiosity rather than rigid judgment, whereas mindlessness is the "auto-pilot" mode that is rigid and governed by routines and assumptions that guide behavior by relying on fixed or "blind" categories and distinctions. Academics have investigated the role of mindfulness in facilitating high-reliability project organization, change, innovation, and flexibility, contrasting routine-based behaviors with those based on mindfulness, and examining the self-regulation of project actors and project teams. Being mindful is becoming more and more of a need in managerial roles and should no longer be seen as an option. It's a

way to prevent harmful effects of stress, keep our brains in top form, and boost our capacity for self-control and sound decision making. The field of megaprojects is the current home of the latest mindfulness research focus. For the first time, the concept of "mindful leadership" has been introduced to the realm of megaprojects, where it is hoped that it will promote openness to new ideas and optimism among team members while also aiding in the management of the stress and pressure that come with dealing with the innate social complexity of such endeavors. Communicating with others in a way that acknowledges their presence and seeks to find solutions to problems without assigning blame is a hallmark of mindful leadership. Mindfulness have shown to have a positive effect on both productive and destructive conflict on project teams working on large-scale endeavors. Attention and mindfulness boost megaproject performance, and especially when the project team is comprised of trained professionals that pay close attention to detail at all stages. The successful management of megaprojects has been linked to the application of mindful management principles, such as paying close attention to the present moment, being open to new information, and processing experiences with acceptance and curiosity rather than judgment. In particular, through allocating consciousness, distancing emotions, and aligning attention, mindfulness processes boost megaproject organizations' resilience (Damayanti et al., 2021; Daniel et al., 2022; G. Wang et al., 2021; L. Wang et al., 2021).

Front End Engineering Development (FEED) is vital for the successful accomplishment of large-scale projects. To help avoid problems in the construction of megaprojects, rational instrumental conceptions try to identify as many commonalities among highly successful people as possible. However, the antagonistic and contingent character of megaprojects, as well as the dynamic complexity of their various pieces, are ignored by these methods. The effectiveness and accomplishment of the megaproject's planning phase can be defined and measured by constructing a process-oriented framework that places an emphasis on project characterizations and the authority of stakeholders. Megaproject development performance and its relation to project success needs more definition, basis and clarification (Ben Abdallah et al., 2022).

Organizations with dedicated "Project Management Offices" (PMOs) can better manage many large-scale projects at once by working with both internal and external stakeholders to ensure seamless integration from the ground up in the construction process and improved teamwork. There are six ways in which businesses can benefit from adopting such organizations to better deal with the complexities of management issues such as procedures, decisions, coordination, alignment, supervision, as well as reducing ambiguities. They use the information gained from working with a wide range of subcontractors to inform their decision making and improve the efficiency of their delivery methods. It has been emphasized that megaproject management literature is still in its infancy, and more investigation is required to comprehend the causes and effects of these massive, complex endeavors. As a result, the megaproject management system as a whole, during the course of the project's entirety, requires significant modifications aimed at filling in the gaps. There are no established norms for improving the management of future megaprojects and implementing a comprehensive management structure. It has long been a source of stress for a number of well-known businesses because the completion of their megaprojects never seems to come in on time, under budget, or with the necessary number of satisfied customers to satisfy the expectations of their investors (Turner & Xue, 2018). That's why it's crucial to have a fully integrated and carefully controlled PMS from start to finish. In the past, projects were managed on an ad hoc basis, with the aid of charts and other makeshift methods and instruments. But more effective instruments and approaches are needed for efficient management. Project success requires four components to match with the contextual dynamics of the project: the project's plan, method, people, and power (Mesly, 2017).

It is critical to have a deeper familiarity with the full lifecycle of megaproject creation and implementation. There are still numerous open questions that need to be answered effectively in the field of megaproject management, including those related to the projects' very existence and dominance, composition and governance, performance, accomplishment and failure, and societal difficulties (Ashkanani & Franzoi, 2022). Building trust between a client and a service provider, vendor, or contractor is crucial during any project. It improves cooperation, which becomes less burdensome as the incentive to monitor the other parties wanes (Cook et al., 2005). Trust can also serve as a replacement for control, hence reducing the agency costs inherent to various project delivery approaches. Trust is often linked to knowledge transfer and quality management in endeavors like the creation of new IT systems (Park & Lee, 2014). In addition to formal contracts, inter-organizational collaborative innovation projects utilize trust to preserve unique funds (Wu et al., 2017). In addition, trust's influence on projects' outcomes is often assessed in terms of how it encourages high-performance teams and boosts productivity. Also, it's viewed as a potential threat, implying that there's no ambiguity when there's 100% trust but a lot of it when there's just 10% trust and 10% information. Megaprojects, which are characterized by their tremendous complexity, shall cultivate a trusting environment (Cerić et al., 2021).

Megaproject success is contingent upon the project manager's ability to overcome complicated obstacles. A. J. Shenhar, (2001) slated that success of the megaproject management approach is reliant on external factors (degree of complexity, project manager's level of leadership competency). Success rate enhances (but not guaranteed) due to the presence of these three factors: (1) low social complexity; (2) an emotionally and socially competent megaproject manager; and (3) a competent and flexible megaproject manager (Damayanti et al., 2021).

There needs to be more theoretical investigation of the many forms of organization and institutional frameworks being formed among megaproject stakeholders to enhance megaproject success (Gil & Pinto, 2018). There is a need for more study into the application of public private partnership structures and hybrid organizational forms (Quélin et al., 2017). Further study is required to establish if and how modern digital technologies like AR, AI, and manufacturing production methodologies can be used to complete megaprojects (Gosling & Naim, 2009). Modularity in large-scale construction projects could benefit from off-site manufacturing in high-volume industries (Tee et al., 2019). Examining how various styles of leadership might be adapted to meet the challenges of modern and emerging organizational structures is essential. Understanding how the infrastructure will be built in a setting characterized by shaky institutions, fluid and developing regulatory frameworks, and pervasive corruption is essential (Locatelli et al., 2017). Realizing this is crucial and investigate the institutional and cultural variables that have a role in the planning and execution of megaprojects worldwide. Additional study is required to understand how stakeholders' responsibilities and the often-conflicting interests, requirements, and goals of stakeholders affect the outcomes of megaprojects. More information is

required to understand on the corporate diplomacy at play in the coalition's communications with the megaproject's financiers, regulators, affected areas, and users (Henisz et al., 2014). Hundreds of separate agreements with contractors, consultants, and subcontractors make up the supply chains for megaprojects. While previous research has identified some of the capabilities system integrators need to coordinate suppliers and forge collaboration, it's unclear how much capability clients and system integrators need to create in-house or how they should disintegrate megaprojects into components undertaken by contractors and suppliers (Davies & Mackenzie, 2014; Denicol et al., 2020). The current body of literature does not provide a thorough knowledge of megaprojects as a production system, which would include but is not limited to planning, design, manufacturing, building, integration, and handover to operations. Research in the future could shed light on how the many components of megaprojects function in tandem to boost performance (Müller-Mahn et al., 2021). There has never been a time when it was more important to pick the right projects and make an informed assessment of their economic, social, and environmental consequences (Thoufeeq, 2022).

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